
PERMEABILITY-ENHANCING DRYING ADDITIVES - A PERSPECTIVE FROM *IN-SITU* ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

The drying process of hydraulic bonded refractories represents a crucial bottleneck to the widespread adoption of this significant class of materials. Mitigating the risk of explosive spalling is of paramount importance as it entails extended heating procedures, resulting in substantial CO₂ emissions and reduced end-user productivity. To minimize the occurrence of such explosions, two commonly deploying strategies involve the utilization of semi-empirically defined temperature plateaus and the incorporation of permeability-enhancing additives. Among these later, polymeric fibers have emerged as a preferred choice due to their cost-effectiveness and efficacy. Nevertheless, despite the ability to tailor various properties such as fiber melting temperature and melt viscosity, the underlying mechanisms by which these synthetic materials enhance permeability remain not clearly understood. Hence, the present study proposes the use of neutron tomography to provide insights into the influence of these fibers on the drying process. Notably, alterations in the velocity of the drying front and moisture accumulation were quantified. The anticipated outcomes of this investigation encompass advancing fundamental understanding of these mechanisms, providing practical guidelines to optimize the potential of polymeric fibers in averting explosive spalling, thereby inducing safer and faster drying processes for refractory castables.

INTRODUCTION

Drying is a process in which water is extracted from a partially or completely saturated porous material through various mass transport mechanisms, such as the diffusion of water molecules and capillary pressure driven flow [1]. These phenomena occur due to gradients in pressure, temperature, concentration or a combination thereof, leading to the removal of moisture from the material [1].

This process can even occur at room temperature depending on the environmental relative humidity thanks to the imbalance in the partial pressure of water vapor between the gaseous mixture present within the material's porous structure and the one in its surroundings. An analogous behavior is observed when washed laundry is hanged for drying after washing.

In the context of refractory castables, where quick procedures to reach operational conditions is essential, the intrinsic permeability is low, the structures have significant dimensions, and water is also present as free and combined forms, thermal gradients are frequently employed to control and induce faster water withdrawn [1, 2].

Still, this is the most time-demanding stage within the refractory castables processing route, impacting directly the costs with energy consumption and, most importantly, the production halt of products that involve high temperature processes [3].

The risk of explosive spalling, which refers to the sudden and destructive failure of the refractory castable which arises from the combined effects of pressurized water vapor trapped within the material's pores and thermomechanical stresses [4], is the main reason for the extended time length of the drying stage, as the use of slower heating rates and temperature plateaus prescribed by semi-empirical laws are the most common strategies to ensure safe drying of the lining [1, 2].

As shown by Cunha et al. [5], the aforementioned strategies result in large energy consumption and may actually be an overconservative approach. A distinct line of development on this

matter is the study of composition optimization to mitigate the risk of pressurization and, ultimately, explosive spalling [6]. This can be carried out through the incorporation of polymeric fibers into the castable composition, which increases its intrinsic permeability during the heating process.

Much has been theorized about the mechanisms of permeability enhancement of the compositions containing fibers. For instance, Zhang et al. [7] have proposed that the inclusion of polypropylene fibers may induce the formation of microcracks due to thermal expansion differences between the polymer and the castable matrix. On the other hand, Innocentini and colleagues have proposed that the enhancement could arise from the melting of the fibers and their subsequent burning out [8]. However, as highlighted by the recent review by Mohammed [9], the precise manner in which these additives improve the spalling behavior of concrete remains elusive.

This leads to a conundrum: even though synthetic polymers can be meticulously tailored to have properties that fulfill multiple concurrent requirements, a definitive guideline regarding the specific attributes that the optimal drying additive should possess is currently lacking.

The efforts to study this class of additives include: i) permeability measurements [8]; ii) differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) characterization of the fibers' behavior during heating [7]; iii) thermogravimetry analysis (TGA) of the compositions or the additives themselves [1]; iv) explosion tests (TGA performed with high heating rates in equipment designed to withstand extreme conditions) to assess their effectiveness to prevent explosive spalling [1]; and v) electronic micrography analysis after the drying process, which cannot determine which microstructure features were originated during the test, or the cooling, or even in the sample preparation [7].

More recently, Stelzner et al. [11] investigated the moisture transport and reconfiguration (determined by the bonding state of water) in high-performance concrete (HPC) either with or without PP-fibers using X-ray-CT and ¹H NMR. Results showed that the samples with the permeability-enhancing additive exhibited a faster drying front. Moreover, the dried zone (DZ) after the heating procedure was 40% longer in the PP-containing sample, and the total moisture content at the samples' bottom increased by approximately 5 vol.% and 2 vol.% for the fiber-free composition and the containing one, respectively, after heating. However, the study did not compare different additives, and the mechanisms behind the increase in permeability were not thoroughly discussed.

Barakat et al. [12] explored the drying process of refractories incorporating polymeric fibers through NMR experiments. It was found that the increased permeability during fiber melting speed-up the water removal and reduced both the drying front temperature and the resulting maximum pressure. However, the results didn't quantify the water distribution or fiber placement.

Recently, neutron tomography was used to observe directly the drying of refractory castables providing unequivocal proof of the accumulation of water that occurs at the innermost position of the sample, also known as the "moisture clog phenomenon" [13]. Additionally, the heating rate effect on the moisture clog was studied and it was found out that higher heating rates resulted in a faster and longer lasting water accumulation at the innermost position of the sample [14].

Thus, the current work aims to apply neutron tomography in-situ observation methods to compare the behavior of refractory compositions with different types of fibers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The current study considered high alumina castable compositions with 5 wt. % of calcium aluminate cement, consisting of tabular alumina and calcined and reactive Al_2O_3 . As a drying additive, polypropylene, polyethylene or cellulose fibers were added and the detailed castables compositions can be found in Table 1. It should be noted that changes in the water content were necessary to ensure similar levels of flowability for the samples with distinct fibers and the reference material without any drying additives. Also, the weight percentage of the fibers was different as the cellulose fiber is less dense than its synthetic counterparts, and it was decided to maintain the volumetric fiber content constant for all different additives tested.

Tab. 1: High alumina refractory castables compositions considered in the current study.

Raw Materials		5CAC (wt.%)	5CAC-PP (wt.%)	5CAC-PE (wt.%)	5CAC-Cel (wt.%)
Tabular Alumina (Almatis)	AT 6-3	18	18	18	18
	AT 3-1	10	10	10	10
	AT 1-0.5	11	11	11	11
	AT 0.6-0.2	9	9	9	9
	AT 0.2-0	16	16	16	16
Calcined and reactive alumina	CL370, Almatis	11	11	11	11
	CT3000SG, Almatis	10	10	10	10
Calcium Aluminate Cement	Secar 71, Imerys	5.0	5.0	5.00	5.00
Drying Additive	PP, supplied by RHI-Magnesita	-	0.1	-	-
	PE, Emsil-Dry, Elkem	-	-	0.1	-
	Cellulose, Suzano	-	-	-	0.2
Distilled Water		4.5	4.7	4.6	5.4
Dispersant	Castement FS60, Basf	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2

The castables without additives, with PP and PE fibers, were obtained following the standard protocol of pre-mixing the powders for 1 minute in a regular rheometer. Next, the water was added, and the composition was mixed for an additional 3 minutes. The sample with cellulose fibers was obtained using a different methodology. As its mechanism is based on the swelling of the fibers, before the castable preparation, half of the water added to the composition was mixed with the cellulose fibers in a bench mixer for 5 minutes. After that, the mixture of water and cellulose was added to the castable, following similar protocols to the ones used for the other compositions.

Afterwards, the compositions were cast in dense alumina cylindrical ceramic casings with internal diameters of 3.6cm and 5cm high with open ends (the bottom part was closed with adhesive tape during casting and curing) for the neutron tomography tests.

The experimental layout of the in-situ drying tests is present in Figure 1. The sample is dried from an infrared heater placed close to its top surface. The heating rate applied was $20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ up to 600°C , with a plateau afterwards for 30 additional minutes. The whole setup is fixed on a turntable table with screws. To fill the gap between the sample and the Teflon container, and to avoid lateral heating, a thermal insulator is used. Regarding the sample, Figure 3 b), shows

a slice of the neutron tomography highlighting the impermeable ceramic casing. Finally, it should be noticed that the samples were placed in the opposite direction of the casting.

Fig. 1: (a) Experimental set up for the neutron tomography test in the NeXT equipment at Institut Laue-Langevin (ILL) and (b) vertical slice of the 3D reconstruction of the neutron tomography of the sample showing the alumina casings.

The neutron tomographies were acquired using the NeXT instrument at the Institut Laue-Langevin (ILL). The true spatial resolution was around $190\ \mu\text{m}$ whereas the time interval between two successive tomographies was 58.5s, as described in the tests reported by Tengattini et al. [15]. After the tests, the 3D volumes were reconstructed using the Feldkamp filtered back projection using a commercial software (X-act, by RX Solutions).

Considering the post-processing of the images, the drying front progression used for calculating the sizes of the dried zones (DZ) volumes was obtained through a gradient based algorithm, visually described in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Drying front position detection algorithm. Firstly, the mean of the intensity value on the radial direction was calculated inside the region of interest, then a Savitzky-Golay filter was used to reduce the noise of the data. Finally, the minimum of the derivative of the radial mean intensity with respect to the height defined the drying front position, which is represented by the blue line (notice how it is defined by the maximum of the yellow line on the derivative plot).

A different method also used to quantitatively analyse the evolution of the water content during drying was the calculation of the normalized intensity evolution over slices of the sample. This is calculated using the ratio between the intensity of an image at a given moment and the median of the first 10 tomographies (representing the initial state before drying).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mass loss between the sample preparation and the experiment execution (the storage aging mass loss) and after the test is summarized in Table 2. It is possible to see that all samples lost between 2 wt.% to 7 wt.%, regardless of the composition.

Tab. 2: Summary of the water loss of each sample. All percentages are calculated as a fraction of the total water added in each composition.

Test	Composition	Storage Aging Mass Loss (wt.%)	Experiment Mass Loss (wt.%)
1	5CAC	3.1%	9.4%
2	5CAC	4.2%	7.5%
3	5CAC-PP	3.3%	14.4%
4	5CAC-PP	4.4%	17.6%
5	5CAC-PE	3.0%	15.4%
6	5CAC-PE	2.2%	14.5%
7	5CAC-Cel	5.9%	20.7%
8	5CAC-Cel	3.5%	21.9%

Direct comparisons between different samples using the data of Table 2 are not possible as the tests did not have the exact same duration, nonetheless, an overall trend can be identified when considering the experiment water removal, with the reference 5CAC composition without any additive displaying the smallest amount of water removed, followed by the PE and PP samples. The samples with cellulose were the ones with the highest quantity of water lost during the drying test.

In order to draw a clear comparison between the different tests, a relative time scale, t_r , is considered, in which the initial time is defined by the start of the drying front progression obtained through the methodology depicted in Figure 2. Axial slices of the normalized intensity sample are shown in Figure 3. It is possible to see that the sample with no additives (5CAC) was indeed the one with the smallest dried region (the area characterized by a smaller normalized intensity - in blue - at the top of the sample).

The evolution of the mass transport within the composition containing PP fibers showed a more intense drying between $t_r = 0$ min and $t_r = 12$ min, however, the size of the dried zone (DZ) remained similar to the 5CAC composition. At the end, the DZ is roughly 1.5 times bigger than the one seen on the sample with no additives.

The 5CAC-PE sample showed a moisture distribution at $t_r = 12$ min similar to the reference composition. This might highlight a permeability enhancing mechanism that starts later when compared to what is seen for the 5CAC-PP and 5CAC-Cel. The final condition shows a larger DZ than 5CAC, suggesting that the water removal rate increased over time. Moreover, the dried zone is not as intense as the other compositions containing additives.

Finally, 5CAC-Cel shows a fast and intense drying that proceeds with a constant water removal rate, as the DZ is the largest at both $t_r = 12$ min and $t_r = 20$ min and it has the smallest values of normalized intensity.

To further investigate these observations, quantitative analyses considering the relative drying volume percentage are presented in Figure 4. The reference composition was the one where the water removal was the slowest. For instance, it took around 30 minutes to reach the 20% of relative drying volume. That mark was reached after only 18 minutes for the 5CAC-PP, 13 minutes for 5CAC-PE and 10 minutes for the 5CAC-Cel. This is directly linked to the different mechanisms of actuation of the fibers.

Fig. 3: Normalized intensity at 0 min, 12 min and 20 min of relative time, t_r . This temporal scale considers the initial time ($t_r = 0$ min) as the beginning of the drying front progression detected by the gradient based algorithm.

It is known that cellulose can lead to higher permeability even before reaching 110° C [6], due to the removal of water from the swelled fibers, thus leading to a faster water withdrawn at presumably smaller temperatures. Polypropylene and polyethylene, on the other hand, depend on thermally-activated changes of their state that take place at higher temperatures [6, 7, 8], leading to the initial behavior closer to the reference one. After that, the permeability increases and the process is faster than in the 5CAC samples.

Fig. 4: Relative drying volume versus the relative drying time for all compositions. The dried volumes were obtained from the drying front position detection algorithm presented in Figure 2.

To investigate the influence of fibers on the moisture clog, the evolution of the normalized average gray value within a disk of the sample was analyzed, as shown in Figure 5. Among the compositions studied, the 5CAC composition exhibited a more prolonged moisture accumulation period (marked by gray values higher than the initial ones), while the 5CAC-cellulose composition showed a shorter duration. However, the total moisture accumulation was slightly more intense and occurred at a significantly faster rate. This observation indicates that the enhanced moisture transport occurs in both directions, towards the hot surface and into the center of the sample. The increased permeability, though, eases the rapid withdrawal of this accumulated moisture, before dangerous higher temperatures are reached, resulting in a faster and safer drying process. Similar behavior was observed for samples containing polypropylene (PP) and polyethylene (PE) fibers.

Fig. 5: Normalized averaged gray value evolution for the central disk of the sample, shown in the inset.

Thus, when considering unidirectional drying, additives that rely on mechanisms that are triggered at too high temperatures might actually be not as beneficial, as the entrapment of moisture can still take place in the colder regions of the refractory castable and potentially induce explosive spalling.

CONCLUSIONS

The understanding of the drying process in refractories castables holds great potential for reducing the carbon footprint of the processing of these materials, thanks to the long drying curves, which are often overly conservative. Efforts to provide safe and efficient drying of refractory castables entail cheap and readily available additives that won't affect any of the required properties during their use.

Polymeric fibers have emerged as the most promising and widely adopted choice. Thus, the objective of this study was to investigate the impact of various permeability-enhancing additives from an unprecedented perspective. By employing neutron tomography, the drying process of compositions with polypropylene, polyethylene, cellulose fibers, or with no additives was observed in real-time.

It was found out that the 5CAC sample was the one with the smallest drying zone after the test followed by 5CAC-PP and 5CAC-PE. 5CAC-Cel was the one with the largest portion dried, indicating faster water removal with a constant drying rate. The moisture clog observed when cellulose was used was also the largest one observed, while being the shortest one in duration. The composition with no additive showed the longer lasting moisture accumulation.

In future works, modifications in the current methodology will be explored to enable the direct examination of the thermal behavior of fibers, aiming at uncovering the underlying mechanisms responsible for the increase of the castables' permeability. Once these mechanisms are better understood, synthetic fibers could be

engineered to enhance their effectiveness, or alternative natural fiber options could be explored based on similar mechanisms. This approach would further contribute to greener practices, ensuring secure and faster drying processes.

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